

Localisation of the SDGs:

Guidelines for policy makers on introducing the Sustainable Development Goals to the local governance scheme

Katerina Antoniadi

EU CEDEFOP Research Assistant | UNU-MERIT | MSc in Sustainability Science & Policy

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/katerina-antoniadi/>

Introduction

The world is constantly changing. Some needs remain the same while others appear less important in particular geographical areas due to their different priorities. According to Brundtland's report:

“Sustainable Development is the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (WCED, 1987).

Based on the aforementioned, there are three main pillars of sustainability that represent the main aspects of human life on the planet. These are economic growth, environmental protection and social equality (Brundtland, 1987). All three are interrelated and interdependent. Thinking schematically, they could be placed on the vertices of a triangle. A change in one of them affects the other two sides. Of course, in reality the described system is much more complex compared to the simple theoretical approach. Still, this explanation provides a useful first insight on the interlinkage between human society, its activities and the environment (Antoniadi, 2018).

In order to find balance between the pillars, “the Heads of State and Government agreed to set the world on a path towards sustainable development through the adoption of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development¹. This global development agenda includes 17 Sustainable Development Goals, or SDGs, which set out quantitative objectives across the social, economic, and environmental dimensions of sustainable development” (SDG Cities, 2016). The number “2030” refers to the years by which the countries are committed to achieve the Agenda's goals. With the adoption of the SDGs, countries and cities faced challenges that lead to one common question: “How do we operationalize these global goals?” (SDG Cities, 2016). The practical complexity challenges significantly everyone committed to meet the goals of the future.

This paper examines the Sustainable Development Goals under the spectrum of SDG 11 namely, Sustainable Cities and Communities. First, it will briefly introduce all the 17 SDGs followed by a more detailed approach of SDG 11. Moreover, it presents the United Nations Sustainable Development Solutions Network's attempts to localize the goals in order to adapt them to the needs and capabilities of local areas and cities. The research continues by adopting one of the many possible forms of SDG-localization in pursuit of examining its potential. Finally, it attempts to introduce a method for approaching the concept of localized SDGs by measuring their performance.

¹ For more information, visit <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015/transformingourworld>.

Guidelines for Policy Makers

The following section provides a guide with a step-by-step explanation on how to:

- i) Understand the SDGs' indicators in real life
- ii) "Translate" the indicators into a common language (codification)
- iii) Approach the indicators in small groups of targets (level 1)
- iv) Integrate the results under one particular goal (level 2)
- v) Recognize and analyse the values created by a policy or activity (reflect on the results)

Identity:

It is extremely essential to first define the main characteristics of the examining case as the latter will determine the process' following steps. These characteristics are related to the natural landscape (highland, lowland, seaside etc), natural resources (forest, river, mines etc), climate, locality type (urban, rural), economic activities (primary, secondary, tertiary production sector), social characteristics (population, average age of citizens, active number of citizens etc), main type of governance (top-down, bottom-up etc). However, the aforementioned represent the practical characteristics of a city; social behavior, norms and more generally, culture as a whole are inextricably linked to the immaterial nature and affect directly not only the individuals as such, but also the society as one dynamic living organism. Certainly, it's not feasible to objectively understand such elements but it is extremely important to take into consideration their impact and influence on the local development and governance. For example, the same teaching methods cannot be applied to students with different learning abilities. Similarly, the same set of rules cannot apply successfully to divergent groups of people.

Define relevant indicators:

The United Nations have identified 232 indicators for 17 goals. However, this research examines only those indicators that have been recognized as applicable under the SDG-11. In order to define the latter, the research used a mapping approach as explained below.

The selection is based on the perception regarding the targets' implementation. There are targets whose realization requires the involvement of national or even international authorities. The local actors may play a crucial role, but the decisions depend on a higher level of governance. Therefore, such targets are not included in the list. In order to recognize a target as **eligible**, it has to be demonstrable at a local level without the need for permission on behalf of higher governing bodies. Hence, a question arises:

Q: Is target A demonstrable at a local level without constraints by higher governing bodies due to dependency?

After collecting all the relevant targets and indicators, I examined their "level of connection" with respect to the main SDG-11 targets. It has to be noted, that at this step the focus moves from the target as such to its indicators in order to become more accurate. In other words, there might be targets who have been recognized as "eligible". However, each target has its own indicators and not all of them can be reached at a local level mainly due to lack of authorship or even resources. Thus, the questions developed here were:

Q1: Could the examining indicator be integrated to an existing SDG-11 target?

This particular question could be either positive or negative. In the first case, the indicator is directly integrated. However, if the first question receives a negative answer, a second question appears.

Q2: Could the examining indicator stand separately as an additional target-indicator scheme under the SDG-11 umbrella?

Hence, after checking every element with respect to SDG 11, the findings have been incorporated into one new table, which shows all the targets and indicators that could be reached -at least partly- by local and regional authorities.

Having implied the aforementioned steps, led to a total of 12 targets and 55 indicators which can be examined in the local-level context.

Prioritise:

Every city has its own characteristics and potential as well as needs. Hence, it is reasonable to have different policies and priorities depending on the local demands. It should be noted, that priorities change and adapt to new challenges throughout time. Therefore, it is important to regularly revise the city’s agenda and examine the level of importance for each goal. Likewise, the indicators are not equally important everywhere and tend to dynamically change after a certain period of time. The decision-makers are asked to decide on the importance as this would help understand the indicators’ results in the next steps. In the examining case (see table below):

Level of Importance & Meaning	
1	Less Important
2	Important
3	Urgent

Collect:

Finding and collecting data is a complicated process that requires time and agility and patience. However, it is necessary in order to understand the city's status, recognize its needs and design proper policies. Collecting data will happen within a certain period of time and will continue after that period for the next one². In the examining case, there are three columns stating the real and expected data. The "real" columns indicate the moment the decision-makers have decided to examine the at-that-moment information. It could be defined on an annual basis but also after a shorter or longer period. The "expected" column shows the tendency for that particular indicator. For example, the goal for the unemployment rates would be to have a reduction. Thus, the tendency would show a reduction ↓ . On the opposite direction, a willingness to increase the percentage of green spaces would have a positive tendency ↑ . Sometimes, it can be possible to define the tendency in detail in case the decision-makers have certain numerical goals in their agenda. Note though that it is not necessary to include a number.

The table below is indicative. It is highly recommended to avoid using it as such without prior consideration of its relevance to the case one would like to use it or without following the previous steps described in this document. No scores are included.

² Since the process is dynamic in its whole, the same applies to its parts and smaller steps. Hence, data collection should not stop; rather data information should be examined after a certain time-period previously defined by the decision-makers. This way, it will be more efficient to examine progress and move towards the next steps, those of implementing decisions, having a real-life practical impact and analyse all the relevant results.

Indicators	
	The indicators below have been chosen randomly after having examined if they apply to the criteria described in the previous steps.
a1	Proportion of population living in households with access to basic services (water, sanitation, electricity, heating)
b1	Proportion of population that has convenient access to public transport, by sex, age and persons with disabilities
b2	Death rate due to road traffic injuries
f1	Recycling rate, tons of material recycled
h2	Proportion of population completing mandatory school
i1	Coverage of protected areas in relation to marine areas
k9	Proportion of youth (aged 15–24 years) not in education, employment or training

Score			Metric System
Real ₂₀₁₈	Expected	Real ₂₀₁₉	
	↑		
	↑		
	↓		
	↑		
	↑		
	↑		
	↓		

Importance		
1	2	3

Comments

Code:

As mentioned in the previous step, each indicator gives their own and distinct results, which have a particular meaning for what they represent. These results though, cannot be used altogether in the following steps; it is important to create a common basis and subsequently, avoid potential misinterpretations. Therefore, the Codification phase acts as a transition from the different results to a series of numbers/words which can be studied in a common framework.

There are several ways for coding with the simplest of them being to calculate the percentages. Certainly, someone may use a different approach, which is permitted as long as the indicators are not misused, the results can be properly interpreted and there are no biases that could alienate the process. This paper will use the percentage approach in order to keep it less complicated.

Level 1:

After having similar codified data, the indicators can be approached under the same functions.

Parameter:

- **Weighting based on importance:** there are often indicators that need to be prioritized over others due to decisions by the local/regional authorities. For more information, see “Prioritise” section.

Target 11.1
By 2030, ensure access for all to adequate, safe and affordable housing and basic services and upgrade slums
General Form:
[indicators' scores]
[number of indicators]
$(a1 + a2 + a3 + a4 + a5 + a6 + a7 + a8 + a9 + a10 + a11)$
11

Level 2:

Same procedure as in Level 1, this time for the goal. At this step, instead of inserting the indicators in the function, one has to insert the targets meaning that the latter should have been calculated first. The parameters remain also the same as previously.

<u>Level 2</u>
Goal 11
Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable
$(A + B + C + D + E + F + G + H + I + J + K + L)$
12

Refecation & Design:

Reflecting can be both objective and subjective depending on the approach a decision-maker may follow. To begin, objectively one could judge the results “satisfying” or “negative” simply by comparing the numbers representing the facts to those representing the expectations. Such a comparison though, would lack a concrete and clear explanation on the results’ origins as well as factors that affected them. Hence, it is necessary to take into consideration elements such as:

- Implemented policies which may support some targets more than others
- Necessary funding
- Level of collaboration among stakeholders (in terms of communication, resources, discussion etc.)
- Identity (both practical and immaterial)
- Time: the moment of calculation plays a decisive role because every indicator and every target cannot be simultaneously implemented at the same level of success. For example, the number of tons of material recycled every year would need less time to be calculated than that of the atmospheric footprint of a city.

Arrows:

The arrow stands for repetition. Performance measurement is an iterative process, which supports the dynamic lifespan of a policy, project or activity at a local and regional level. It is important to note that the results might differ in every single stage of a process, mainly due to the factors of time and decision making. After a certain period of time, decision-makers should keep in mind to re-consider the indicators they are using in order to make sure that most of the aspects of their policy are properly examined. It is possible that there will be no changes in the indicators list and that is of course, acceptable. It is also good to stay informed about the city's characteristics, hence, the city's identity. In case of significant changes, it is necessary to re-define the next steps; otherwise, the scheme will be trapped in a vicious cycle based on non-applicable to reality data.

Decisions and policies are dynamic processes that need to be assessed in every step of their progress in order to achieve positive results. It is essential to monitor and follow every single step from the design, to the implementation and finally, evaluation of a project. Such an approach would provide all the necessary data, which would serve as a black box to the particular project -thus, a major help for identifying any related factors and circumstances- but also as a guidance for any upcoming projects -what lessons can be derived-.

References

- Antoniadi, K. (2018). *Urban labs as a new form of urban governance: public value creation and its measurement*, Zenodo <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2431689>.
- Brundtland, G. H. (1987). *Report of the World Commission on environment and development: "our common future"*. United Nations.
- Getting Started with the SDGs in Cities: A Guide for Local Stakeholders (2016, July 13). Retrieved from <https://sdgcities.guide/>.